

A Reference Model for Security Level Evaluation: Policy and Fuzzy Techniques

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Abstract: In a world made of interconnected systems which manage huge amounts of confidential and shared data, security plays a significant role. Policies are the means by which security rules are defined and enforced. The ability to evaluate policies is becoming more and more relevant, especially when referred to the cooperation of services belonging to un-trusted domains. We have focused our attention on Public Key Infrastructures (PKIs); at the state of the art security policies evaluation is manually performed by technical and organizational people coming from the domains that need to interoperate. However, policy evaluation must face uncertainties derived from different perspectives, verbal judgments and lack of information. Fuzzy techniques and uncertainty reasoning can provide a meaningful way for dealing with these issues. In this paper we propose a fuzzy technique to characterize a policy and to define a Reference Evaluation Model representing different security levels against which we are able to evaluate and compare policies. The comparison takes into account not only minimal system needs but evaluator's severity, too; furthermore it gives clear information regarding policy weakness that could be used to help security administrators to better enforce rules. Finally we present a case study which evaluates the security level of a "legally recognized" policy.

Key Words: Policy, Public Key Infrastructure, Security Evaluation, Fuzzy Techniques

Category: K.6.5, K.4.2

1 Introduction

In recent years, due to the large diffusion of distributed systems, there has been a large need for security grants to fully trust a system. To achieve this goal, it is necessary that systems which produce and exchange documents (especially digitally signed and legally recognized documents) should be able to guarantee a certain "security level" and demonstrate their trust-ability.

The problem of resource sharing among wide infrastructures is relatively new in Computer Science; in most classical architectures, shared resources are part of one system with one centralized security mechanism enforcing access control rules. In contrast, a distributed architecture is composed of several sub-systems representing specific domains and each one has to face its own security issues; to let them interoperate, mechanisms must be found to integrate them. These mechanisms, of course, involve heavy security management issues which could make the whole system weak.

In this paper we focus on Public Key Infrastructures (PKI) [Housley, 1999, Ford, 1997, Curry, 2000] and on the rules that a Certification Authority (CA) has to follow or implement to guarantee a certain "security level" to the users certified in its domain. The need for a clear definition and selection of security rules has led system administrators to formally face system security and management by means of policies which are composed of a set of security rules and allow:

1. a clear separation of the rules which govern the system's behaviour from system functionalities [Lupu, 1999];
2. a more flexible system for managing changes in user and service access rights [Damianou, 2001, Jajodia, 1997].

Since a formal definition of Security Level does not exist in literature, this represents a big problem to face [Lupu, 1999, Casola, 2002] because it is not possible to extend trust to other domains based on assertions like: "the system is secure enough to...". To face this problem we think that it is possible to start from security policies to formally describe the behavior of a system, and so formally characterize all security critical aspects. After formalization, the "extending trust" issue (cross certification [NIST, 2001, Turnbull, 2000]) could be performed through policy *evaluation* and *comparison* [Grill, 2000].

In this paper we propose a security policy evaluation technique to handle such problems; we will focus on certificate policies of Public Key Infrastructures (PKIs) but the technique is not limited to this field. Our start points are:

1. A Certificate Policy (CP) is a set of rules and provisions which must describe all the security procedures that a Certification Authority (CA) has to follow in order to guarantee different services to users and other CAs.

2. Currently CP are written in free textual ways but several efforts are being made to formalize them [Chokhani, 1999]; this is a very critical point especially in the Cross certification.

A CP template to formalize provisions in an unambiguous way has been presented in [Casola, 2002, Casola, 2003] where each technical and not-technical provision is represented as a numeric or enumerative data-type. The formalized policy is a structured set of all provision instances. It is very useful to write a policy and immediately locate different provisions between the two policies but, a global evaluation mechanism was never proposed. Since policies are usually written in free textual words, an effective policy evaluation cannot avoid dealing with the semantics of free textual words. This fact inspired us to adopt fuzzy models to better address this aspect [Hosmer, 1992] and to propose a fuzzy-based policy evaluation technique.

Through fuzzification we gain a higher expressive power, an enhanced ability to model real-world problems, and, above all, a methodology for exploiting the tolerance for imprecision. By allowing soft analysis, fuzzy set theory [Zadeh, 1965] does not force precision where it is not possible as other approaches did. Fuzzy sets have a natural capability to express and deal with observation and measurement uncertainties, they are more attuned to reality than crisp sets [Klir, 1995].

In a security context, fuzzy numbers allow us to represent whether or not a security provision is guaranteeing an expected security level through a verbal judgement; this will help us to better model vagueness of words and judgments related to technical and non-technical provisions. In particular, each security provision can be assessed with an ordinal judgment label used in our approach to define a fuzzy number for each provision. The most important result of this approach is that the overall policy evaluation will be obtained by aggregating fuzzy values representative of security provision assessment.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: in Sections 2 and 3 we will illustrate the context in which the certificate policy evaluation could be a big problem to face for Cross Certification, and we will illustrate our approach for policy formalization to help security administrators in performing such an evaluation. In Section 4 we will illustrate some details regarding the fuzzy theory and how we have used it to characterize and analyze a policy. In Section 5, a Reference Evaluation Model is proposed to evaluate and compare policies. In Section 6 a case study is presented to illustrate and validate all the steps of the proposed technique through an example of policy comparison. Finally the proposed technique is briefly summarized and some conclusions are presented.

2 Security Background

According to RFC2459, a certificate policy is "a named set of rules that indicates the applicability of a certificate to a particular community and/or class of application with common security requirements" [Housley, 1999]. At present, a certificate policy standard does not exist; in the PKI field, this is a very huge problem, especially during the comparison process, when two different Certification Authorities (CAs) need to extend trust to each others in order to allow interoperability among their users and, at the same time, guarantee the declared security levels.

The action of extending trust is usually referred to as Cross Certification and it usually involves the cooperation of both technical and organizational people from the CAs that need to trust the other parties in order to completely understand if they are able to interoperate in terms of technological implications and are able to guarantee the same security level to their users.

This problem is currently dealt with as an "organizational problem": security experts, from both the technological and the organizational field, manually evaluate the different provisions implemented by the two CAs and, by manually comparing each provision, they finally decide to cross certify them or not. The novelty of digital signature technology and the diverse perspectives of policy makers, including legislators, industry representatives, and the organized association, have resulted in divergent approaches for resolving key issues within different jurisdictions; for this reason, up to few years ago, there were very different models of certificate policies.

In particular, the policies were different with regard to their structures and with regard to the critical provisions included in them; indeed, each organization could decide which technologies to adopt and above all the liabilities and responsibilities involved in the use of digital signatures (for example that in Italy a digital signature has "legal validity").

Cross Certification is not simple at all, since it involves not only technological aspects (partially resolved by the standard X.509 [Housley, 1999], PKCS families, and so on) but, above all, organizational and liabilities-related aspects. There are a lot of examples available on the Internet [Curry, 2000, Turnbull, 2000] in which, to simplify their work, each CA builds a table with all its critical security provisions on the rows and, on the columns, they respectively put the provision instances implemented by the two CAs and only after an accurate evaluation of all of them, they could decide to cross certify or not. In addition the building and evaluation of this table is not simple, because it is not obvious that the two CAs consider critical the same provisions and it is not obvious that technical and organizational people agree on the evaluation of the single provisions.

As previously mentioned, there is no standard format, standard list of topics, or standard procedures for a policy; nevertheless, because the provisions of

different policies need to be compared, we need a commonly-agreed approach to structure the policy contents, in order to quickly identify their similarities and differences. We therefore need a structured and formalized policy model, to:

- help users to decide more easily which policies satisfy their requirements, and which certificates can thus be accepted by their applications;
- help applications to automatically accept trusted certificates issued by other domains;
- help CAs to decide which certificate policies from other security domains can be considered equivalent, by helping security experts from different fields.

Furthermore, it is much easier to compare policies if they are presented not only in a unique structured way but also if the very complex objects described are formalized as simple types; in this way, in fact, it would be possible to establish some logical relations or comparison criteria among them. In the following sections we will illustrate a way to formally represent a policy and a fuzzy technique to automatically evaluate it.

3 Policy Formalization

In this section we report some results of previous works on policy formalization since we will use them to implement the technique of the next section. As previously mentioned, a certificate policy standard does not exist. Recently, some efforts to formalize PKIs certificate policies and related security provisions have been produced; the formalizations proposed in [Mendes, 1995, Klobucar, 1999, Casola, 2002, Casola, 2003] help system and security administrators in the policy life cycle management.

In effect, all policy frameworks present wide limits; they certainly represent a valid means for developing a textual policy, but they do not resolve ambiguity problems, they are not sufficiently structured to be used as a valid means for evaluating and comparing policies.

Probably, as mentioned before, the most detailed and relevant suggestion for the formal presentation of certificate policies was described in the Internet RFC3647 [Chokhani, 1999]. It is not a standard but it is currently widely used by all the Internet Community and for all these reasons we have decided to choose its main provisions and structure for the first steps of our formalization.

We primarily underline that the framework is structured as a hierarchical tree. Textual provisions were refined in a fine-grain and a grammar to automatically compare them was proposed in [Casola, 2002]. We will adopt this approach to define a policy formalization, it consists of three steps:

Step 1) definition of macro-provisions;

Step 2) definition of second level provisions;

Step 3) XML language definition.

As mentioned above, the RFC3647 is a good example of policy formalization so we have decided to use its structure to implement the first two steps of our method. All the macro-provisions are very complex objects, categorized for different topics, which need to be addressed in a Certificate Policy. According to the RFC3647, the first level of provisions includes:

- Introduction,
- General Provisions,
- Identification and Authentication,
- Operational Requirements,
- Physical, Procedural and Personnel Security,
- Technical Security Control,
- Certificate and Certificate Revocation List (CRL) Profiles,
- Specification Administration.

Second level provisions try to describe all the details regarding all macro-provisions and they express objects which are still complex but bring more bounded security information; for example the *Technical Security Control* provision includes: *Key Pair Generation, Private Key Protection, Other Aspects of Key Pair Management, Activation Data, Computer Security Controls, Life Cycle Technical Control, Network Security Control, Cryptographic module engineering controls*.

At this point we have defined the main provisions of our structure which are actually filled with textual descriptions. The provisions defined in the first two steps are very complex objects and this is the most important reason of ambiguity; to solve ambiguities, the proposed model supports a hierarchical structure which consists of several couples (element-type, value) representing topics and sub-topics, where the "value" itself is a complex object. A wide range of new data-structures has been defined to represent the values, and finally a grammar has been created based on such a data-structure set to formalize a certificate policy. The data-structures used are new atomic or enumerative types and total order relations among their values may be defined, so as to solve the ambiguity

problem. For most critical topics we were able to build such a structure which could be automatically processed by a numeric algorithm.

The proposed structure is a hierarchical tree which can be represented by an XML document; tree nodes identify complex security provisions, leaves identify simple security provisions [Casola, 2002, Chokhani, 1999, Casola, 2004]. Now we will present some significant examples.

Example 1. XML Structure of the provision: *Private Key Protection*:

```
<PrivateKeyProtection>
  .....
  <PrivateKeyProtectionBOX>
    <PrivateKeyNoProtection>...</PrivateKeyNoProtection>
    <PrivateKeyOnLocalPC>...</PrivateKeyOnLocalPC>
    <PrivateKeyOnFloppy>...</PrivateKeyOnFloppy>
    <PrivateKeyOnSmartCard>...</PrivateKeyOnSmartCard>
    <PrivateKeyOnSmartCardWithBiometricSensor>.....
    </PrivateKeyOnSmartCardWithBiometricSensor>
  </PrivateKeyProtectionBOX>
  .....
  <PrivateKeyEscrow>...</PrivateKeyEscrow>
  <PrivateKeyBackup>...</PrivateKeyBackup>
</PrivateKeyProtection>
```

Example 2. XML Structure of the provision: *Publication Repository*:

```
<PublicationRepository>
  .....
  <FrequencyPublication>
    < PolicyIssuanceFrequency>...</ PolicyIssuanceFrequency>
    < PublishedCertificateIssuanceFrequency>...
  </ PublishedCertificateIssuanceFrequency>
    < CRLIssuanceFrequency>...</ CRLIssuanceFrequency>
    < FrequencyDay>...</ FrequencyDay >
    <FrequencyHours>...</FrequencyHours >
    <FrequencyMinutes>...</ FrequencyMinutes >
    <FrequencySeconds>...</ FrequencySeconds >
  </FrequencyPublication>
  .....
</PublicationRepository>
```

Based on the elements of Example 1 and 2, being enumerative or numerical types, it is possible to define a total order relation. Thanks to the tree structure of the document, in which every "textual" provision or any other data element is represented by a specific node which has to be father, child or brother of any other node element, it has been possible to represent the relationships among the elements of the policy without any ambiguity. As shown, there are some very simple types that primarily correspond to quantifiable parameters (key length, CRL publication period, etc), they are usually used in available literature when comparing policies. Other elements have a more complex and structured representation and the applicability of our method to these elements is the main contribution of our formalization.

We have used it to easily compare "single statements" by using a simple XML parser; however the process is still semi-automated, it could help when:

1. The relying parties want to find specific provisions of the policy to trust, for a more accurate analysis.
2. The relying parties want to fix the trustworthy conditions to be used when comparing policy provisions.
3. It is possible to define logical relations for an automatic comparison on parametric values.

Indeed, the main feature of that approach is that it enforces a formalization even on non-numerical provisions, this is the case for a lot of organizational and non-technical provisions whose semantic usually carries very critical information; the risk of a discrete formalization is the inevitable loss of information; for this reason, we decided to adopt a fuzzy technique which is capable of dealing with uncertainties of words.

4 Policy Fuzzy Characterization

Proposed formalization helps us to highlight all the security provisions that a CA has to assure. We need, now, a way to express a judgement regarding the overall quality of a given instance of the policy, in order to compare and classify different proposed policy instances.

In order to derive the overall evaluation of PKI security policies, we need to aggregate successively all simple provision evaluations to obtain a final global judgement. The final judgement, that is the aggregating result, should be:

- expressed in intelligible format according to the security evaluators;
- useful to the evaluator to gain a better understanding of the meaning and risk of decisions he will take.

4.1 The Problem of Policy Evaluation

Effective security of systems for an organization is not easily quantifiable and/or qualifiable: the evaluation of security policies must deal with the evaluation of security technical provisions which are partially qualitative and therefore uncertain. The main issue is to define a suitable model capable of aggregating the evaluation of each provision into a reliable index expressing the policy quality. Indeed, we could mainly view this as a Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) problem [Bellman, 1970]. The simplest way for dealing with MCDM problems consists in transforming qualitative assessments into numbers, in order to aggregate them with quantitative information, usually by means of minimum (*min*), maximum (*max*) or weighted averaging (*wa*).

An example can be useful: let us consider only two security provisions: `<KeyDmension>` and `<SignatureAlgorithm>`, where the first one is evaluated as *good* and the second one as *bad*; a "minimum" aggregator will say that the policy is *bad*, a "maximum" aggregator will give a final evaluation of *good* and a "weighted averaging" aggregator will give an intermediate judgement such as *sufficient*.

Min, *max* and *wa* can be considered special cases of aggregation operators [Calvo, 2002]. An aggregation operator is a map:

$$F_n : K^n \longrightarrow K \quad (1)$$

Where K is the (numerical) set wherein assessments are expressed. Usually it coincides with an interval of numbers; often it is made up of numbers bounded in $[0,1]$. Aggregators must respect some axioms, such as:

- boundary conditions: aggregation of mins (maxs) leads to min(max) result;
- monotonicity: aggregation of better scores cannot lead to worse results.

Another way for dealing with MCDM problems consists of aggregating data on a continuum built along an ideal line of increasing optimism from min to max operator. This method is suitable for managing and resolving intermediate situations between severe and indulgent decision making attitudes.

A well-known class of aggregation operators is Ordered Weighted Averaging (OWA) [Yager, 1988, Yager, 1993]. An OWA operator is defined as:

$$F(a_1, \dots, a_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i a_{p(i)} \quad (2)$$

where $p(\cdot)$ is a decreasing ordered permutation of n elements a_1, \dots, a_n . Weights $w_i \in [0,1]$ and are such that

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1 \quad (3)$$

They express how much we wish to put into prominence best (worst) results and are not related to the importance of the elements. An important measure associated to OWA operators is *orness* (σ) defined as:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (n-i)w_i \quad (4)$$

The orness varies within $[0,1]$ according to weight distribution. Such a relationship is not one to one: different distributions can lead to the same orness.

There are three important special cases of weight distribution worth pointing out. When $w_n = 1$ and $w_{i \neq n} = 0$ we get $\sigma = 0$. Thus we can say that aggregation coincides with min operator and the selected orness value can model a "severe" decision attitude in which n given decreasing ordered elements are evaluated by the worst element. On the contrary, when $w_1 = 1$ and $w_{i \neq 1} = 0$ we get $\sigma = 1$ and we can say that aggregation is equivalent to max operator and the selected orness value can model a severity decision attitude in which n given decreasing ordered elements are evaluated by the best element. When $w_i = \frac{1}{n}$, $\sigma = 0.5$ and aggregation is the arithmetic mean operator where best elements and worst elements are balanced.

All aggregations always lie between min operator and max operator, previously defined, moving through the arithmetic mean. We can refer to the orness value as a measure of evaluation severity. For example, the more the orness value is low, the more the aggregation is close to a min operator and the more the evaluation will be severe.

Thus when we move from the arithmetic mean to min operator, that is towards a lower orness, the trust in the aggregation increases; in any case we should not pass the level of $\sigma = 0.5$. On the contrary, when we are interested in the best values of the provisions, we should adopt a high orness, such as $\sigma = 0.7$. Practically thanks to the orness measure it is possible to introduce the evaluator severity level during policy evaluation. In fact, security evaluators have different decisional attitudes.

4.2 Fuzzy Judgements

Moreover, evaluation of policies should deal with uncertainty of qualitative assessments which cannot be modelled by usual (crisp) numbers. Fuzzy numbers are more suitable for capturing and representing the imprecision of technical and non technical provisions. For example, imagine that an evaluator considers the clause `<ContactDetails>` which contains the name of the person in charge of the policy and he wants to compare two instances of a given policy which differ with regard to the name the person in charge. In particular the evaluator might need to point out which person in charge is more reliable, that is the evaluator

needs to express a judgement on the quality of the person in charge. In this case fuzzy judgements are a big help in the evaluation. Fuzzy set theory provides an exact representation of concepts and relations which are vague or imprecise.

This theory, with the associated logic, named fuzzy logic, was proposed by [Zadeh, 1965]. A fuzzy set is a set, A (in a Universe X), without a sharp borderline contrary to classical (crisp) sets. In fact in a fuzzy set each element may belong (membership degree = 1) or not (membership degree = 0) at the set or have degrees of membership between 0 and 1 but in a crisp set elements must have either 0 or 1 as the membership degree.

We are particularly interested in a special type of fuzzy sets: the fuzzy numbers, which are often represented with triangular and trapezoidal membership functions. Fuzzy numbers are largely used to express and model judgments [Bellman, 1970, Zadeh, 1972], taking into account vagueness of words and qualitative assessments.

Evaluation could be made by ordinal scales. Each term of the scale is represented by a label and labels are ordered in an increasing way, too. For example if four different judgments on a single provision should be expressed, the corresponding labels could be: *poor*, *average*, *good*, *optimal*; if we assume that values can be uniformly comprised between 0 and 1, an ordinal numerical value should report *poor* as 0, *average* as 0.33, *good* as 0.66 and *optimal* as 1. Of course for each judgement we could choose a less or more fine-grain scale, this is usually denoted as the granularity or resolution of the scale.

By using triangular fuzzy numbers, a judgment on the scale can be represented by a pair (p,s), where p is the ordinal position of the label in the chosen scale of judgment (for example the label "good" has the 3rd ordinal position in the previous scale, so p=3) and s is the number of labels considered by the scale i.e. the granularity or the resolution of scale (in the previous example s=4). Then these pairs are translated into fuzzy numbers with triangular shape. Their shape is characterized by these characteristic points:

$$x_L = \frac{p-2}{s-1}; x_M = \frac{p-1}{s-1}; x_R = \frac{p}{s-1} \quad (5)$$

The distance between x_L and x_R determines the base of the triangular shape and x_M determines its vertex orthogonal to the base. For instance if the judgment "good" is the fourth on a scale of five (p= 4, s= 5), we get $x_L= 0.5$, $x_M= 0.75$, $x_R= 1.0$. Differently if it is the fifth on a scale of seven (p= 5, s= 7), we get $x_L= 0.5$, $x_M= 0.66$, $x_R= 0.83$.

Figure 1 illustrates an example of a fuzzy representation of a scale of five terms whose labels are *very low*, *low*, *medium*, *high*, *very high*. The top of the figure shows the verbal judgments, while the numerical values on the x-axis are the ordinal positions x_L , x_M and x_R . Of course the triangle width depends on the scale resolution. An interesting result of this approach for modelling judgements

Figure 1: Triangular Fuzzy Representation of a Scale of five Terms

is that the x_M , named core, could be interpreted as a traditional crisp judgment, while $x_R - x_L$ could be interpreted as an index of the fuzziness of the judgment.

We explicitly note that if a provision is not implemented at all in a security policy, the security system is heavily affected and a very negative judgment should be expressed on it; this situation is modelled as a particular triangular fuzzy number with $x_L=0$, $x_M=0$, $x_R=0$ that is with a crisp zero. With this particular number we are able to express the worst judgment (zero) with no uncertainty (crisp).

4.3 OFNWA Aggregation

The aggregation operators used in our work are named Ordered Fuzzy Number Weighted Averaging (OFNWA); they were proposed in [Canfora, 2001, Canfora, 2002]. OFNWA operators are able to maintain uncertainty and incompleteness of information thanks to a built logical model where dependencies among criteria are modelled over a set of inferential rules. Thanks to the OFNWA operators, which aggregate fuzzy numbers into a fuzzy number, each policy, that is to say its single provisions, will be completely characterized by a couple of parameters:

- the support, represented as $[x_L; x_R]$;
- the core, represented as the value x_M .

With regard to our security context, x_M will be associated to the assurance level of each policy while the support will be representative of the fuzziness related to the result on the assurance level. So, in our analysis we will show how these parameters effectively represent the security level guaranteed by a policy and we will give a security-related interpretation to the orness value. Moreover, in

[Canfora, 2003a] an appropriate importance model was introduced. Such model is based on the iterative application of the two following logical assertions:

- p1: if importance(Ci) is high then aggregation should consider Ci;
- p2: if importance(Ci) is low then aggregation can ignore Ci.

The existence of this importance model is in accordance with another aspect which must be taken into account in security evaluation that is to say, the different relevance that criteria assume in the evaluation of PKI. The relevance parameter depends on the particular evaluator profile and his needs. For example, an end-user will stress differently criteria compared to a developer or a security administrator. Further, the result of OFNWA aggregation can be automatically computed according to different orness values thanks to a implemented fuzzy tool introduced in [Canfora, 2003b]. This tool offers:

- verbal judgements scales to statically evaluate the local quality/security of simple provisions. Once that these scales are identified, security experts can translate the verbal ordinal scales in fuzzy numbers;
- a graph structure (named evaluation graph) for hierarchically organizing the set of selected simple security provisions;
- decision graphics representing with curves how some characteristics of final evaluations change according to orness values.

4.4 Decision Graphics

Decision graphics were proposed in [Canfora, 2003a]. An example of these graphics is shown in figure 2. From this figure an evaluator can observe graphical results of the global security level of selected policies. The related example will help the reader to understand how an evaluator could read decision graphics and highlight her/his decisions. These graphics are obtained by processing four different instances of a built evaluation graph for a given security policy. The selected instances differ only in one target provision, for which the same scale (granularity 4) and four different values *low*, *medium*, *high*, *very high* were selected. In particular we used for this provision the fuzzy numbers relative to the respective four pairs (p,s): (1,4) (2,4) (3,4) (4,4).

As shown in figure 2, there are two types of graphics:

1. orness variable graphics (left side);
2. x variable graphics (right side).

Figure 2: Decision Graphics Example

Orness variable graphics are shown on the left-hand side of figure 2 where the orness value is represented on the x axis, while the aggregation result is represented on the y axis. Since each triangular fuzzy number can be completely described by the support $[x_L; x_R]$ and the prototypal value x_M , the evaluator can analyze how these characteristic points change by changing the orness value in the interval 0 (where the evaluator’s severity is maximum) and 1 (where the evaluator’s severity is minimum) that is to say the evaluator can obtain three corresponding curves, changing the orness, named x_L , x_R , x_M . In particular in our figure we can observe four terms of these curves, one for each instance of the given policy.

By analyzing these graphics, the evaluator can get information concerning the impact of the uncertainty of the initial judgements on the global security level of a selected policy measuring the distance between the curves x_L and x_M and the curves x_M and x_R . Increasing these distances, fuzziness of the evaluation grows and indeed, the use of different verbal scales, leads to results with a different degree of uncertainty too.

In our figure we can observe that these distances grow by changing the orness when the value of the target provision changes. Moreover we can observe that when orness is lower than 0.5 the final judgement is not affected: when the orness is low, the severity of the evaluator is high, so even if one clause is better, the worst evaluation affects the judgement. Note that at orness 0, the evaluation

is zero crisp, so there is a non stipulated provision.

The right-hand side of figure 2 shows the *x variable graphics*. By changing the orness in the interval [0,1], the evaluator can obtain the triangular fuzzy numbers representative of the selected policies instances evaluations for each selected orness value. These graphics help the evaluator to better understand the aggregation continuum provided with OFNWA operators.

Thanks to this information the security evaluator gains a better understanding of the meaning and the risk of the decisions she/he will take. The evaluator can observe that the ranking of selected different policies depends on the considered orness too. Practically, decision graphics give the security evaluator the possibility to assume a different perspective in the analysis of final results and uncertainty, and make more conscious decisions. This will be illustrated in more detail in sec. 6.

5 The Reference Evaluation Model

Thanks to the proposed approach we are able to evaluate a policy, but our primary target is to compare different security policies to extend trust to other CAs or, more in general, to be able to define the security level involved with a policy.

For this reason, we need a mean that helps system administrators to classify a given policy instance. Classification should be made through comparison with reference levels and their formalization. So, we define "Reference Evaluation Model" (REM) the following 4-pla:

$$REM = \langle P, G, S, W \rangle$$

where:

P is a set of policy instances which represent different security levels.

G is an Evaluation Graph;

S is a set of scales for each leaf of the evaluation graph G;

W is a collection of weights for the evaluation graph edges.

The REM will contain all the information needed to classify a given policy instance against a given certification authority. In order to better explain our approach, in this paper we have chosen a particular REM where: **P** is the set of policy instances which represent different security levels, for our REM, we have decided to choose the four policies of the Government of Canada "Digital Signature and Confidentiality Certificate Policies for the Government of Canada PKI" [Canada Government, 1999]; as the Government itself states, they represent four different security levels whose certificates could assure four different

Figure 3: Evaluation Graph

classes of services; furthermore, these policies are structured according to the formalization of the RFC3647 so the formalization process proposed in Section 3 can be completely reused. G is the Evaluation Graph defined in Section 4 whose provisions have been defined in Section 3; as previously mentioned, it was built starting from the formalization proposed in Section 3, so G is strictly related to the chosen set of policies P and the structure of the P policies is the same as the G evaluation graph. Figure 3 shows a little screenshot of the graph adopted in the following.

The judgment on provisions can be chosen among labels/values expressed on scales with different granularity. Each scale represents the possible assurance levels that each security provision can guarantee: different granularity is representative of a different number of assurance levels (for each security provision). For example the provision Bit Length of the previous example is a simple numeric provision whose typical values are: 512, 1024, 2048 bits. So, we associate a scale of just three values to this provision whose labels could be *rudimentary*, *medium*, and *high*; and, according to the ordinal definition introduced in [Casola, 2003], if we have a policy in which Bit Length is 1024 bit, then, we give the judgment of "medium" to this provision.

Figure 4: Verbal ordinal scales

Figure 4 shows the scales used in this work; in particular we have used the following three ordinal scales:

- *rudimentary, high*;
- *rudimentary, medium, high*;
- *rudimentary, basic, medium, high*.

These scales have respectively a granularity of 2, 3 and 4. Technicians can provide their evaluation expressing a preference on the scale which best fits the confidence in discriminating levels. A higher availability of information can lead to a higher confidence in assessment; thus, more precise verbal ordinal scales can be adopted. By contrast, scarcity of information can lead to the choice of less precise scales. Scale values are ordinal labels, they need to be expressed in fuzzy numbers, a fuzzy triangular number is built as described in section 4, so the fuzzy number associated to the provision BitLength= 1024 bit (medium label $p= 2$, $s= 3$) are: $x_L= 0$, $x_M= 0.5$, $x_R= 1$. In conclusion, S is the map of all security provisions values in verbal judgment scales; we explicitly note that a scale needs to be defined for each provision so, like \mathbf{G} , it depends on the chosen set of policies \mathbf{P} . Finally, \mathbf{W} is the set of weights, for simplicity, for this REM, we will use only weight equals to "1", the reason is simply related to the fact that we consider all provisions critical and this is the case of our set of policies. Thus, by applying the policy aggregation analysis on the set of policies \mathbf{P} , using \mathbf{G} as an evaluation graph, \mathbf{S} the set of scales and \mathbf{W} for the weights, we obtain the REM.

In Figure 5 we could graphically represent the evaluated "reference policies". On the right-hand side of Figure 5 we can notice the four reference security levels for a fixed DM severity level (x-variable graphics) and on the left-hand side of figure 5 the four reference security levels are mapped again but for each DM severity level (orness variable graphics). In particular, the left-hand side shows how x_L , x_M and x_R values change, varying the orness value; this shows the behaviour of a policy against the orness: increasing the orness value and

Figure 5: Decision Graphics for Security Policy Levels

Figure 6: Decision Graphic Prototypal Values for Security Levels

therefore decreasing the DM severity the global reference security level grows. The right-hand side graph shows the triangular fuzzy numbers with a fixed orness value (0.3). To help in evaluation understanding, we have added Figure 6, which contains only the prototypal values and Figure 7, which shows four graphics with increasing orness values (respectively 0, 0.3, 0.7 and 1). We can explicitly observe that:

Figure 7: Security Levels Decision X-variable Graphics

- a) with orness zero, the fuzzy number of level one is a zero crisp value, due to the presence of no stipulation provisions;
- b) lower policy has always a lower evaluation compared to higher policies
- c) when the orness grows, the security quality of each policy grows, but a policy of level i never exceeds a policy of level $i+1$.

Points b) and c) exploit the correctness of the approach: policies considered more secure by a PKI, are evaluated as better policies even when the severity of the security administrator grows.

6 Security Evaluation

In this section we will use the REM to evaluate a target policy. The evaluation process is composed of the following steps:

- Evaluate the target policy according to the Section 4 using G, S and W of the chosen REM.
- Compare the result with the "reference policies".

It is important to point out that the formalization process of the target policy will be carried on using the tree built on the reference system (G). With the REM we are able to evaluate a policy from the "point of view" given by the

Figure 8: Decision Graphic for Notariato Policy

CA which has formalized the set P . In order to show the effects of this choice we will apply the described process on a real policy that comes from a completely different policy system.

The policy we evaluate, is the "Manuale operativo del Consiglio Nazionale del Notariato" policy [Notariato Italiano, 2002]; it is an Italian policy legally recognized by the CNIPA. Italian law asserts that a digital signature is fully equivalent to a "manual" signature if the private key and the binding certificate used by the signer are issued by a legally recognized Certification Authority and the Notariato is one of them.

It is important to point out that the Italian policy has a policy model different from the one adopted in Canada; for example it is written in the Italian language, it has different mandatory provisions and, furthermore, the provisions are structured in different ways. This is the biggest problem in the cross certification process, however, as already said, we dealt with it by making the policy formal through the REM G, S and W components. Mainly this has implied the adoption of the same subset of provisions and the adoption of the same judgment verbal scales to compare them with the same evaluation graph.

Figure 8 shows the decision graphic (orness variable) of the Notariato policy using the G, S, W components of the REM for the aggregation. We can explicitly observe that with high severity (orness near to zero) the evaluation is zero fuzzy,

Figure 9: Decision Graphic Prototypal Values: comparison between Notariato and Security Policy Levels

really low, but it rapidly increases when the orness grows. This is due to the fact that the Notariato policy comes from a different CA and it is built upon different security criteria. This rapid increase means that only few provisions are different from the choices of the Canada CA, but there are also provisions that are not stipulated at all and they become predominant for orness= 0.

Figures 9 and 11 compares the Notariato policy with the set P of reference policies (the first one reports the prototypal values in the orness variable graphic, while the second shows the complete decision graphics). Figure 10 compares the Notariato policy and the reference policies with x-variable Decision graphics at orness 0, 0.3, 0.7, 1.

In the following we will assume that x_{Ltp} , x_{Mtp} , x_{Rtp} is the triangular fuzzy number characterizing the Notariato policy, while x_{Li} , x_{Mi} , x_{Ri} $i = 1..4$ are the reference policies fuzzy values.

We can explicitly note that

– x_L :

$$orness < 0.3, x_{Ltp} \leq x_{L1} \leq x_{L2}$$

$$orness > 0.3, x_{Ltp} \geq x_{L2} \leq x_{L1}$$

– x_M :

Figure 10: x-variables Graphics for Notariato and Security Policy Levels

Figure 11: Decision Graphic: comparison between Notariato and Security Policy Levels

$orness < 0.3$, $x_{Mtp} > x_{M2}$ and $x_{Mtp} < x_{M3}$

$0.3 < orness < 0.9$, $x_{Mtp} > x_{M3}$ and $x_{Mtp} < x_{M4}$

$orness > 0.9$, $x_{Mtp} = x_{M4}$

– x_R :

$orness < 0.5$, $x_{Rtp} > x_{R3}$ and $x_{Rtp} < x_{R4}$

$orness > 0.5$, $x_{Rtp} > x_{R2}$ and $x_{Rtp} < x_{R3}$

So if the security analyst strictly adopts the Notariato policy, it will be evaluated as level 2. But if he proceeds in the analysis he can see that the Notariato policy lies between level 2 and 3 with orness lower than 0.3, but then it lies between level 3 and 4.

Our analysis underlines that a severe security analyst has to choose level two for the Notariato policy even if only a few provisions affect the security of the policy, which usually lies between level 3 and 4. In the context of cross certification the right choice should be level 3 , even if some little adjustments on the policy could be applied.

These results can be adopted in two ways:

- by the two CAs (Notariato and Canada Government) to understand what are the differences in their choices and on which clause(s) they need to act on to perform a cross certification;
- by the Notariato CA to update its policy so that it can be better evaluated by the Canadian rules.

7 Conclusions

In this paper we have presented a technique that helps security administrator to analyze, compare and classify in terms of security levels security policies. The proposed technique is able to evaluate the policies by means of a fuzzy aggregation model, in order to take into account both technical and non-technical provisions. The fuzzy evaluation method is the basis for the building of a reference model to classify and analyze policies.

The technique is based on the following steps:

- Choose the set of reference policies.
- Build a Reference Model:
 - Formalize the Reference Policy and build the Evaluation Graph G .
 - Choose the judgment scales S for each Security Provision (G leaves).

- Choose the importance values set W for the G edges.
 - Evaluate the Reference Policy instances using G, S, W .
- Formalize the target policy using the same graph adopted in the REM (G)
 - Evaluate the target policy using G, S, W .
 - Compare the target policy with the reference security policies.

We have shown how to formalize the policies (section 3), how to evaluate them using the fuzzy technique (section 4) and how to build the REM (section 5), verifying that the evaluation method gives us valid results using the Canadian Polices as reference. Finally we have applied the technique on a case study (section 6): a real certificate policy that comes from a legally recognized CA (Notariato Italiano) which works in a country with a different legislation compared to the one that defines the security levels.

In conclusion we have shown that our analysis helps the administrator to understand which is the best way to improve a policy and helps the involved CAs to understand how to perform Cross Certification. An interesting result is that the rigorous classification of the Notariato policy in terms of the Canadian rules will lead to an underestimated security level, but, with our technique we are able to point out that just a little improvement on some provisions of the Notariato policy, increases the security level.

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